

EXPERIMENTAL AND VIRTUAL TECHNIQUES FOR CRACK PROPAGATION ANALYSIS IN COMPOSITE BONDED JOINTS

G. Meneghetti[°], M. Quaresimin*, M. Ricotta[°]

[°]Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Padova

Via Venezia, 1 – 35131 Padova (Italy)

*Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova

Stradella S. Nicola, 3 – 36100 Vicenza (Italy)

giovanni.meneghetti@unipd.it, marino.quaresimin@unipd.it, mauro.ricotta@unipd.it

SUMMARY

Crack propagation observed in fatigue tests of single lap bonded joints in composite material is analysed. Three different techniques are compared: the first one is based on direct experimental observation of fatigue damage evolution, while the other two ones are indirect methods for crack length estimations. In particular the second one is based on a master stiffness curve, the third one is based on a finite element virtual model of the cracked bonded joint.

Keywords: bonded joints, fatigue crack propagation, finite element analyses, single-lap, stiffness.

INTRODUCTION

Several experimental observations [1-5] show that the fatigue life of a bonded joint in composite as well as in metallic material is characterised by a nucleation phase, where one or more cracks emanate from critical locations, followed by a propagation phase, during that the nucleated cracks grow up to a critical length. In the case of composite bonded joints, the crack nucleation phase can take from 10% up to 90% of the total fatigue life, being usually higher in the case of spew fillet joints. Then a fatigue assessment procedure based on the observed damage evolution should take into account and modelling both the life spent during the nucleation phase and that spent in the propagation phase. Under these assumptions, a model for the life assessment of bonded joints in composite material suitable for describing both phases has already presented by the authors [6]. The nucleation phase is described by assuming the generalised Stress Intensity Factor of the local stress field as a parameter suitable to rationalise the fatigue life to crack initiation. The life spent in the propagation phase is obtained by the integration of a power law relating the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) to the crack

growth rate. In previous papers [4,7], the authors presented two different methods for evaluating the crack growth rate from laboratory joints. The former [4], in the following called “*experimental*”, is completely based on direct observation of damage evolution by means of an optical microscope; the latter [7] is based on an indirect evaluation of the crack length evolution by means of the measurement of the joint stiffness drop during the fatigue life. This method will be referred as “*stiffness based method*”.

In the present paper, after a brief description of the previous methods, a third methodology, based on finite element analysis and which will be called “*virtual method*”, is proposed. The new results are successfully compared with those obtained by the application of the “*experimental*” and the “*stiffness based method*”.

MATERIAL, GEOMETRY AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Single lap bonded joints, manufactured from autoclave-moulded laminates (Seal Texpreg® CC206, T300 twill 2x2 carbon fibre fabric/ET442 toughened epoxy matrix) and bonded with the two-part epoxy adhesive 9323 B/A by 3M were fatigue tested under tension-tension loading (nominal load ratio $R=0.05$). Their overall geometry is shown in figure 1. The procedure followed for bonding together the laminates is described in [7].

The influence of stacking sequence ($[45/0_2]_s$ and $[45_2/0]_s$), layer orientation at adhesive-adhrend interface, geometry of the end of bonded area (square edge and fillet) and overlap length (20 and 40 mm) on the evolution of fatigue damage mechanisms was investigated. The test frequency was kept in the range of 10÷15 Hz, depending on the applied stress level.

Figure 1: Geometry of the single lap bonded joint ($w = 20$ and 40 mm, adhesive thickness 0.15 mm) and details of the corner geometry SE = Square Edge joint; F = Fillet joint.

Joints were subjected to repeated blocks of fatigue loading at constant amplitude, up to failure. Damage evolution was monitored by measuring the stiffness drop and also via periodical inspections by eye and by means of a Leica Metallux 3 optical microscope (50x and 100x), equipped with a Leica camera DC 100 providing a geometrical accuracy of 0.05 mm, on the polished edges of the joint. The stiffness drop was monitored by measuring the instantaneous joint stiffness as the ratio between the imposed load range, measured by the load cell, and the resulting range of the actuator stroke, measured by the displacement transducer of the testing machine. In the case of $[45_2/0]_s$ joints only, the stiffness trend was also monitored by using an extensometer

with a gauge length of 25 mm, supplied by MTS. For 20 mm overlap length joints, the extensometer was positioned over the bonded area, as shown in figure 2a. On the contrary, in the case of 40 mm overlap length it was located over one of two edges of bonded area (see figure 2b).

Figure 2: Schematic view of position of the extensometer in the case of 20 mm overlap length (not in scale) (a) and picture of the assembly in the case of 40 mm overlap length (b).

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD FOR CRACK PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

As already discussed, the total fatigue life of a bonded joint can be separated into two distinct phases: the first part spent for the nucleation of cracks and the second spent in the propagation of cracks/delaminations up to a critical length, characterised by specific damage pattern and mechanisms. The reader is referred to [4,5] for a more detailed description. In this paper, the main results are summarised for clarity.

According to [4], the crack onset was defined when one of the cracks emanating from the corners (named as A, B, C and D) and measured on the polished edges reaches a length of 0.3 mm, as shown in figure 3a.

The definition of a “technical” crack was necessary due to two main reasons:

- the practical difficulty in detecting cracks smaller than that size, especially for square edge joints;
- the need for identifying precise, even though conventional locations for the damage analysis. In fact in the case of fillet joints, cracks nucleated mainly as indicated in figure 3, but were also observed to initiate, in very few cases, at the upper corner point between the adhesive and the laminate free surface.

On the basis of this definition of crack onset, the number of cycle to crack initiation N_i was identified. By means of the microscope observations, it was noticed that the nucleation at the different corners does not occur simultaneously and that the propagation phase is characterised by complicated crack patterns including interface, interlaminar and intralaminar cracks and delaminations. In order to propose an engineering model suitable for estimating crack propagation lives, the measured crack length a was the projection of the longest observed crack path at each corner of the joint onto the interface line. Finally, the mean value of the four measured cracks a_{exp} was

considered for analysis purposes, thus assuming that cracks symmetrically propagated from the toe of the joints with straight crack fronts [4,5] (see figure 3b).

Figure 3: Definition of the "technical" crack for the conventional assessment of the crack initiation, at the four corners of the joint overlap (a); model assumed for describing crack propagation phase where a_{exp} is the mean value of the four cracks (b).

STIFFNESS METHOD FOR CRACK PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

Being periodical inspections of specimens very time-consuming, an alternative technique for evaluating the crack evolution during the fatigue life has been proposed [7], which can be summarised as follows:

- the axial stiffness trend $K = K(N)$ is measured as a function of the number of cycles N on one or more reference samples; the $K(N)$ function is then correlated to the evolution of the average crack length $a(N)$ measured by means of microscopic observation, thus deriving a master stiffness curve $K(a)$ (see figure 4);
- in the subsequent tests, the crack length evolution is estimated from the measurements of the axial stiffness trend of the tested joint and the master stiffness curve $K(a)$, previously defined on one or more reference samples. Crack lengths thus estimated are referred to as a_K .

Figure 4 reports the normalised stiffness decrease (defined as observed stiffness K at a given number of cycles divided by the stiffness K_i measured at the beginning of the fatigue test) versus the normalised crack length a/w for most of the tested specimens. Despite the scatter shown by the experimental data, a linear rule was assumed to interpolate all the data. More precisely in [7], three trends were considered: the mean stiffness loss evolution, a 35% steeper curve and a 35% flatter curve. The latter curves enabled us to encompass the scatter of all the experimental data.

VIRTUAL METHOD FOR CRACK PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

The above methodologies require observations of the crack length by means of an optical microscope. In order to overcome this phase, a third new technique was developed. This method is based on the stiffness decrease measured by means of an extensometer during the fatigue test of some reference joints and the definition of a corresponding virtual cracked configuration. The virtual cracked configuration consists of a numerical finite element model containing two symmetrical cracks characterised by straight crack fronts and propagating at the adhesive-adherend interface (figure 5): the

crack lengths are such that the stiffness decrease numerically calculated is equal to that experimentally measured. The choice to model the cracks propagating at the adhesive-adherend interface is based on the actual fatigue damage mechanisms. Therefore the proposed method is based on the *a priori* knowledge of the damage mechanisms occurring during the fatigue life.

Figure 4: Decrease of the normalised stiffness vs the normalised crack length for all the available experimental data [7].

Figure 5: Deformed shape of a cracked joint and details of the FE model at the interface crack [8].

The Finite Element (FE) model used for the evaluation of crack length is geometrically non linear in order to capture correctly the out of plane behaviour of the joints. In order to calculate the stiffness decrease, the variation of the relative distance of the nodes located at the same position of the extensometer blades (node j and node k of figure 6 for 20 mm overlap length) was considered in the FE analyses for different values of the crack length.

Figure 6. (a) reference nodes for 20 mm overlap length defined on undeformed configuration; (b) variation of the relative distance of the reference nodes on deformed configuration.

Figure 7: Normalised relative distance between reference nodes vs. the virtual crack length

Figure 7 shows as an example the relative distance ΔS , evaluated on cracked geometry, normalised with respect to that obtained on the un-cracked configuration, ΔS_i , as a function of the virtual crack length, for a given overlap length and load level. For each tested specimen, the length of the virtual crack, a_V , was obtained by equating the numerical stiffness drop to that measured experimentally for the considered number of cycles.

COMPARISON AMONG METHODS FOR CRACK LENGTH ESTIMATION

Figure 8 shows a representative comparison between the evolution of a_{exp} , a_K and that of the virtual crack a_V , for a single specimen. A similar comparison valid for the crack growth rates is reported in figure 9.

Figure 8: Example of crack propagation derived from direct experimental measurements (a_{exp}), from the stiffness based method (a_K) or from the virtual method (a_V).

Figure 9: Example of crack propagation rates derived from direct experimental measurements (a_{exp}), from stiffness based method (a_K) or from the virtual method (a_V)

Having estimated the crack lengths by the three methods, all data were summarised by plotting the crack growth rates versus the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) parameter [8,9]. Figure 10 compares the resulting Paris curves: the best fit line and the 10% - 90%

probability scatter band obtained by considering the crack growth rates from direct experimental crack measurements (a_{exp}) are reported in solid and dashed black lines, respectively; the green solid line is the best fit for data obtained by applying the stiffness based method (a_K); the red line is the best fit for data obtained by applying the virtual method (a_V). A substantial agreement among the three Paris curves can be observed.

Figure 10: Comparison between Paris curve fitted on experimental data (a_{exp}) (plotted) and those generated by using the stiffness based method (a_K) and the virtual method (a_V). Symbols and scatter band are for experimental data.

VALIDATION

All three methods to estimate the crack length are based on engineering assumptions, which simplify the real damage evolution. Moreover, whatever the considered model fitting the experimental data, crack propagation phenomena are affected by intrinsic scatter. The assumption of the Paris' law governing fatigue crack growth along with different models for calibration of its constant leads to deviation between calculated and observed fatigue life for a given load amplitude. Such deviation is evaluated in the present section by estimating the fatigue life of the tested specimens using the three Paris' equations reported in figure 10. Since the proposed models are applied to the experimental data adopted for calibration of the models themselves, deviation between theory and experiment that will be obtained is interpreted by the authors as a lower bound we may expect in cases different from those analysed in the present paper.

When integrating the Paris' laws shown by figure 10, the initial crack length a_i was assumed to be equal to 0.3mm, according to the technical crack assumption described above, while the final crack length a_f was calculated by equating the equivalent SERR to the mode critical value $G_{Ic} = 900 \text{ J/m}^2$, obtained from experimental measurements [6]. Characteristic results are reported in figures 11, where the experimental results and the scatter band calculated for 10%-90% survival probabilities are compared with

estimations. Each adopted model refers to one Paris-like curve reported in figure 10. The equivalent reliability of the three methods proposed can be easily noticed. In the worst case among those analysed, (figure 12), a slight overestimation of the fatigue life was obtained.

Figure 11: Comparison between experimental data and model predictions

Figure 12: Comparison between experimental data and model predictions (worst case)

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a new technique for crack propagation analysis is proposed and validated. It is based on the stiffness decrease measured by means of an extensometer during the fatigue test of some reference joints and the definition of a corresponding virtual cracked configuration. The virtual cracked configuration consists of a finite element model of the joint containing two symmetrical cracks characterised by straight fronts: the crack lengths are such that the calculated stiffness decrease is equal to that experimentally measured. The results of this new methodology have been successfully compared with those of two previous techniques already presented by the authors.

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- the Paris curves obtained by using the different techniques are equivalent from an engineering point of view;
- the assessment of life spent in crack propagation, obtained by using the three different approaches, is in general in good agreement with the experimental results, being however slightly overestimated in few cases;
- the new technique does not require the observation of the actual crack paths developing during fatigue life: only the monitoring of the stiffness decrease of the joints during the fatigue test is required. Therefore it looks quite attractive for the considerable amount of time potentially saved, at least with respect to the experimental method.
- The SERR evaluation requires the development of a FE model for all the presented techniques. The model used for the evaluation of the virtual crack a_V is the same defined for the calculation of SERR components, by using the VCCT method. Thus, no specific efforts are needed.

References

1. Dessureault M and Spelt J K, Observations of fatigue crack initiation and propagation in an epoxy adhesive, *Int J Adhes Adhes*, 1997, **17**, 183-195.
2. Crocombe A D and Richardson G, Assessing stress state and mean load effects on the fatigue response of adhesively bonded joints, *Int J Adhes Adhes* 1999, **19**, 19-27.
3. Ashcroft I A, Abdel Wahab M M, Crocombe A D, Hughes D J and Shaw S J, The effect of environment on the fatigue of bonded composite joints. Part 1: testing and fractography, *Compos Part A-Appl S*, 2001, **32**, 45-58.
4. Quaresimin M. and Ricotta M., Fatigue behaviour and damage evolution of single lap bonded joints in composite material, *Compos Sci Technol*, 2006, **66**, 176-187.
5. Meneghetti G., Quaresimin M., Ricotta M., Influence of the interface ply orientation on the fatigue behaviour of bonded joints in composite materials, *in press*, *Int J Fatigue*, doi:10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2009.02.008.
6. Quaresimin M., Ricotta M., Life prediction of bonded joints in composite materials, *Int J Fatigue*, 2006, **28**, 1166-1176.
7. Lusiani M., Meneghetti G., Quaresimin M., Ricotta M., "Crack propagation assessment in composite bonded joints", Proceedings of ECCM 13, 13th European Conference on Composite Materials June 2-5 2008, Stockholm, Sweden.
8. Quaresimin M, Ricotta M, Stress intensity factors and strain energy release rates in single lap bonded joints in composite materials, *Compos Sci Technol*, 2006, **66**, 647-656.
9. Krueger R, Virtual crack closure technique: History, approach, and applications, *Appl Mech Rev* 2004, **57**, 109-143.